

TWO LIVES, TWO HORNS”: A STUNNING CASE OF TWIN GESTATION IN A
BICORNUATE UTERUS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: A bicornuate uterus is a congenital Mullerian duct anomaly that result from incomplete canalisation, fusion or resorption of the paramesonephric ducts during the period of embryogenesis. It is a fusion anomaly or defect characterised by a uterus with two horns (cornua) connected by a single cervix. It is associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes including recurrent pregnancy loss, preterm delivery, malpresentation, fetal growth restriction and increased Caesarean delivery. Twin gestation within a bicornuate uterus is extremely rare making its documentation clinically important. In such cases each fetus may occupy a separate uterine horn, creating unique physiological constraints and poses significant clinical challenge due to the risk of obstetrics complications. **Case presentation:** We present the case of a 29-year-old G2P1+0 1A, at an EGA of 38 weeks and LCB 12 years ago who presented to our labour ward with complaints of spontaneous labour pain and liquor drainage with no history of headache, blurring of vision or epigastric pain. No preceding history of trauma to the abdomen. She was not a known hypertensive and her first delivery was via spontaneous vertex delivery. She had a working diagnosis of SPE with twin gestation and an unfavourable cervix at term. **Management and outcome:** The patient had stabilization and delivered via caesarean section of live set of dichorionic diamniotic females both with good Apgar scores and both in cephalic presentation. The bicornuate uterus was incidentally identified during the procedure. Each of the twin was occupying a separate horn linked at the lower uterine segment and a single cervical os. **Conclusion:** The case demonstrate that although twin gestation in a bicornuate uterus carries significant risk /complication, favourable maternal and perinatal outcome could be positively achieved. There is need for a high index of suspicion among healthcare workers in low- to middle-income countries where early diagnosis might be a dilemma, high index of suspicion is paramount to reduce morbidity and mortality.

KEYWORDS: Bicornuate uterus (two horns), twin gestation (two babies), Mullerian anomalies.

INTRODUCTION

When there is an abnormal formation and fusion of the Mullerian ducts during organogenesis, Mullerian anomalies occur.^[1] Female reproductive tract; fallopian tube, uterus, cervix and upper two-thirds of the vagina

originates from Mullerian Duct.^[2] Bicornuate uterus occurs when there is failure of unification or complete fusion of the Mullerian duct during organogenesis.^[2] Uterine anomalies account for 0.1% to 3%, and 15% to 25% worldwide in women with an increased rate of

adverse fetal outcomes, malpresentations, premature ROM, preterm delivery, miscarriages and infertility.^[1,2,3] These Mullerian Duct anomalies can be picked during evaluations for miscarriages or infertility and during antenatal visits.^[4] availability of case reports on the subject matter (bicornuate with coexisting twin and severe pre-eclampsia) is scanty.^[3,4] This is a case report on an incidental discovery and a successful caesarean delivery of a rare occurrence of spontaneously conceived twin pregnancy in bicornuate uterus and coexisting severe pre-eclampsia. High index of suspicion.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 29-year-old G2P1+0 1A, at an EGA of 38 weeks and LCB 12 years ago who presented to our labour ward with complaints of spontaneous labour pain and liquor drainage with no headache, blurring of vision or epigastric pain. No preceding history of trauma. Not a known hypertensive and her first delivery was spontaneous vertex delivery.

She was examined and found to have a blood pressure of 210/110mmHG and associated significant proteinuria. Abdominal findings revealed a uniformly enlarged

abdomen with fundal height of 40cm and multiple fetal poles were palpable. Fetal Heart Tones were both normal but the cervix was not favourable. An assessment of severe preeclampsia in a multipara and unfavourable cervix with twin gestation was initially made.

Management and outcomes

She was admitted and samples were taken for urgent packed cell volume, 2 pints of blood were grouped and crossmatched, Serum E/U/CR, FBC and LFTs were also requested for. She was stabilised using MgSo4 according to Hospital's Labour ward Protocol (using Pritchard Regimen) and parenteral antihypertensives. She was counselled for emergency caesarean section which she had. She was delivered of a live set of DCDA female babies weighing 2.1kg & 2.4kg both with good Apgar scores and both in cephalic presentation. The bicornuate uterus was incidentally identified during the procedure. Each of the twin was occupying a separate cornua linked at the lower segment and a single cervical os. The placentae were two attached by a membrane. The mother recovered well without any complication and at the end of puerperium she was counselled and referred for contraceptive method other than intra-uterine contraceptive device.

Figure 1: Biconuate Uterus during Caesarean Section.

Figure 1: An intra-operative diagnosis of biconuate uterus.

Figure 2: Biconuate uterus with normal tubes and ovaries.

Figure 3: Unidentical twins delivered from biconuate uterus.

Ethical consideration

Consent to publish this case was obtained from the patient and she understood that clinical information and pictures will be used in journals and that her identity will be concealed but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Abnormalities of the uterus are seen in clinical practice worldwide. These anomalies originate from defective organogenesis in the form of fusion or canalization of the ducts during development.^[1] The prevalence varies worldwide, especially in LMICs (including Nigeria). They occur in about 5.5% to 6.6% of the general population world over.^[1,5] High prevalence is in infertile women and women with recurrent miscarriage (7.3% and 16.7% respectively).^[5] The Mullerian anomalies includes double uterus with or without a double cervix and vagina, bicornuate uterus or separate uterus and/or abnormalities of the genital tract, cervix, vagina and urinary tract.^[6]

Patients with Mullerian anomalies experience a significant risk of complications more than patients with no Mullerian anomalies.^[7] Although there is significant risk of complications, some women have uneventful pregnancies and have been reported to deliver successfully without complications.^[9] This can explain

the history of previous uncomplicated pregnancy and vaginal delivery in the first pregnancy of the patient in this case report.

The prevalence of bicornuate uterus is 0.4%.^[1,6] There is a risk of miscarriage, preterm delivery and malpresentation in pregnancy coexisting with bicornuate uterus than a didelphys uterus.^[9,10]

There is a very negligible report of women with uterine malformations with coexisting twin pregnancies.^[7] The earliest documented was in 1953^[14] where antenatal ultrasound was done and there is a history of previous uncomplicated deliveries. In the mentioned study, the diagnosis of bicornuate uterus was not made. It can be inferred that the few reports are from the patients with such anomalies having an uneventful pregnancy and labour (as in this reported case's first delivery) or missed diagnosis. Moreover, there may be energy in reporting rare cases like the subject matter. This means there is no available guideline accepted worldwide in managing such cases. From the foregoing, outcome might be catastrophic.

Adam *et al.*^[15] recommended that case reports on uterine anomalies with coexisting pregnancy be published especially if with twin pregnancy. In 2014, Ahluwalia *et al.*^[16] opened the maintenance of a worldwide register to report cases and consistently improve pregnancy outcomes and fetal survival rates in pregnancies with uterine anomalies.^[16] In the case being presented, she could have been missed with a catastrophic outcome in labour if at all she might have progressed. Meaning the SPE as the main reason for operative delivery made the diagnosis possible. The case also highlights the possibility of missing a diagnosis of bicornuate uteri prenatally in LMICs where availability and access to quality obstetric ultrasound and other diagnostic modalities are not accessible. There is need for training in USS for obstetricians in LMICs. There is need for guideline as to managing such cases. This will make favourable maternal and fetal outcomes.

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